

second backcross, which probably resulted from the restricted recombination between parental genomes indicated by the low frequency of rod bivalents in the meiosis of the F₁ hybrids. Furthermore, none of the *O. minuta* allozyme (*Sdh1*, *Pgd2*, *Got1*, and *Got3*) was detected in the 24-chromosome plant, indicating lack of introgression of chromosome segment from the donor wild species.

Cited references

- Glazmann JC, delos Reyes BG, Khush GS. 1988. Electrophoretic variation of isozymes in plumules of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) - a key to the identification of 76 alleles at 24 loci. IRRI Res. Pap. Ser. 134.14 p.
- Jena KK, Khush GS. 1984. Embryo rescue of interspecific hybrids and its scope in rice improvement. Rice Genet. Newsl. 1:133-134. ■

Histological observation of callus morphology in rice

J. O. Narciso and K. Hattori, Laboratory of Plant Genetics and Breeding, School of Agricultural Sciences, Nagoya University, Chikusa, Nagoya 464-01, Japan

We evaluated callus morphology, emphasizing cell compositions of rice varieties, through histological observation.

Callus morphology of five indica (IR54, Rc2, Oboshi, 2757, 2764), two japonica (Nipponbare, Tsutsu), and two javanica (Lemonte, Rinatte) varieties was evaluated in two callus induction media. Varieties showing good callus growth 2 and 4 wk after culture were evaluated through histological observations using scanning electron and light microscopes.

Of the varieties tested, IR54, Toboshi, Nipponbare, Tsutsu, and Rinatte exhibited good callus growth. Callus morphology of each subspecies differed from one another. At 2 wk after culture, calli of IR54 and Toboshi were characterized by two callus masses: one was yellow, compact, and smooth-surfaced; the other yellowish with hairy protuberance and green spots. Japonica varieties Nipponbare and Tsutsu and javanica variety Rinatte had almost similar morphology. Calli of both sub-

1. Dehusked grains of a) indica (IR54), japonica (Nipponbare), and javanica (Rinatte) and b) their corresponding callus types.

species were yellowish, compact, and smooth-surfaced. Slight changes in callus morphology were noted 1 mo after culture. Green spots occupied more than 50% of the whole callus mass in IR54. Calli of Nipponbare and Tsutsu became globular and easily disintegrated into small pieces. Callus of Rinatte became friable. Callus types of the three subspecies represented by IR54, Nipponbare, and Rinatte are shown in Figure 1b.

Histological observation through a scanning electron microscope showed that

2. Scanning electron microscopic observation of the cell compositions in the calli of a) IR54, b) Nipponbare, and c) Rinatte. Scale bars = 300 μ.

Genetic analysis of epicuticular structure involving a dripping-wet leaf mutant of rice

K. Nakamura and K. Hattori, Laboratory of Plant Genetics and Breeding, Nagoya University, Chikusa, Nagoya 464-01, Japan

We obtained a dripping-wet leaf mutant among doubled haploid progenies regenerated from rice (*Oryza sativa* L. cv Nipponbare) anther culture. This mutant

each callus type had a distinct cell composition (Fig. 2a-c). Callus of IR54 showed a large, highly compact cell mass with domelike structures. The surface was rough with corrugations (Fig. 2a). Callus of Nipponbare was made up of compact, globular cell masses of about the same size (Fig. 2b). The cell masses were composed of round cells arranged in layers, like a flower. Callus of Rinatte was composed of small, round, compactly arranged cells (Fig. 2c). Light microscopic observation of the resin sections generally showed darkly stained, meristematic cell clusters.

The results of a study using mungbean suggest that cell types in a callus mass relate to embryogenic potential (Narciso and Hattori 1995). This relationship has not been fully studied in rice. Results of this research could provide the basic information needed to establish this relationship.

Cited reference

- Narciso JO, Hattori K. 1995. Different cell compositions in mungbean (*Vigna radiata* (L.) Wilczek) cotyledon calli. Breed. Sci. 45(2):173-177. ■

was derived from callus treated with 20 Gy of gamma rays 2 d after transfer to regeneration medium. Rice leaves, in general, can shed drops of water; however, leaves of the dripping-wet leaf mutant do not because of their highly hydrophilic leaf surface. Many of these mutant types, which are controlled by a single recessive gene, have been obtained in rice. Some of these gene loci have already been identified (Sato et al 1983). Although factors causing high leaf wettability in these mutants are not clear, leaf surface structure

Scanning electron microscopy observations of the flag leaf blade surface at the abaxial side of a dripping-wet mutant. Nipponbare (wild type) (a and b) dripping-wet leaf mutant (c and d). LP = large papillae, SP = small papillae, S = stomata, P = pili.

is one of the putative causes of wettability. To study the histological basis of leaf wettability, we observed the leaf surface of the newly obtained dripping-wet leaf mutant under a scanning electron microscope.

We observed that the dripping-wet leaf mutant was also an epicuticular waxless mutant. Large and small papillae, stomata, and pili on the mutant leaves were not so different from those on wild types (see figures 1a, 1c). However, the mutant leaf had a plain surface with epicuticular wax less developed than that found in wild types (see figure 1b, 1d). We also investigated the inheritance of epicuticular wax and dripping-wet leaf traits in crosses of mutant type/wild type and wild type/mutant type. The F_1 plants in both crosses were wild types. In the F_2 of both crosses, dripping-wet leaf plants always had the epicuticular waxless trait. The segregation ratio of the wild type to mutant type (dripping-wet leaf and epicuticular waxless) fitted to a 3-1 ratio

in both crosses, indicating that the dripping-wet leaf trait was caused by reduced leaf epicuticular wax.

Many mutants with less epicuticular wax accumulation were already obtained in *Arabidopsis*, barley, and wheat (Lemieux et al 1994). Reduced wax on the leaf surface altered the reflection of light, which allowed isolation of the mutants through visual inspection. These mutants were designated as glossy or nonglaucous mutants. The dripping-wet leaf mutant of rice might be one of these mutants with reduced epicuticular wax.

Cited references

- Lemieux B, Koornneef M, Feldmann KA. 1994. Epicuticular wax and eceriferum mutants. In: Meyerowitz and Somerville, editors. *Arabidopsis*. New York: Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press. p 1031 - 1047.
- Sato H, Iwata N, Omura T. 1983. Gene analysis of some dripping-wet leaf mutants in rice. *Jpn. J. Breed.* 33 (Suppl. 2): 243-243. ■

Embryogenic cell suspensions established from a high-protein purple black rice

Huihua Fu, Tingliang Tian, Biology Department, Central China Normal University, Wuhan 430070, China; and Yingguo Zhu, Biology Department, Wuhan University, Wuhan 430072, China

Establishing embryogenic cell suspensions is important in regenerating plants from rice protoplasts. We studied the effects of explants, media, hormones, and culture suspension procedures on callus induction and cell suspension of indica variety HuaHei 01, a new high-protein purple black rice derived from progenies of Hua 03/Hong Jing 501.

Effects of explants. We cultured explants from young panicles (1-10 mm), anther at mid-uninucleate stage, and mature seeds on Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium supplemented with $2 \text{ mg } 2,4\text{-D L}^{-1} + 0.2 \text{ mg Kin L}^{-1}$. The lowest callus induction (0.4%) was obtained from anthers. Young panicles had high callus induction (24.6%), as did mature seeds (21.3%). Calli from anthers and mature seed were compact, globular, and yellow, and could be used to establish embryogenic cell suspensions. Calli from young panicles were scattered and pale yellow.

Effects of media and hormone ratios. We chose MS, N6, and GM supplemented with different ratios of hormones for incubating explants. AA, N6, and MS with $2 \text{ mg } 2,4\text{-D L}^{-1} + 0.2 \text{ mg Kin L}^{-1}$ was used for the liquid suspension culture. Although the calli induction rate on N6, MS, and GM media did not significantly differ, the quality of calli induced on the various media did. Most of the calli induced on N6 were yellow, compact, and globular, and grew rapidly; those induced on MS and GM grew slowly. Calli in the AA liquid medium remained yellow, while those in the N6 and MS media turned brown in the first month of suspension.

Hormones significantly affected induction frequency and callus quality. Time required for callus induction was shortened, and some calli induced were pale yellow with root hairs when 4 mg NAA L^{-1} , $1 \text{ mg } 2,4\text{-D L}^{-1}$, and $0.2 \text{ mg Kin L}^{-1}$ were supplemented. However, induction